

On Morita equivalence of Lie categories

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Abstract

Ehresmann introduced the concept of Lie categories in [1]. More recently, Grad examined several interesting examples of Lie categories and explored the connections between Lie groupoids and Lie categories ([2]). In this article, we present a notion of equivalence between Lie categories and generalize the Morita equivalence of Lie groupoids to that of Lie categories.

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1 Introduction

Category theory provides a unified framework for mathematics by describing objects and morphisms across various fields. Physicists have adopted this approach, interpreting physical states as objects and physical processes as morphisms, thus forming a category which corresponds to a physical system. In order to provide such a realization of a physical system, category theory intertwines with the theory of smooth manifolds, leading to the concept of a Lie category. The notion of a Lie category was first introduced by Ehresmann in [1]. In the same paper, Ehresmann studied Lie groupoids which are characterized by the additional requirement that all morphisms are invertible. This concept has been explored and continues to be a focus of research.

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Recently, Zan Grad identified many fascinating examples of Lie categories (see [2]). Analogous to the construction of Lie algebroids from Lie groupoids, he developed a similar construction for Lie categories. Moreover, he established sufficient conditions for the set of invertible morphisms in a Lie category to form a Lie groupoid. Additionally, he proposed a method for building Lie categories that can describe physical systems using the idea of entropy, and found that the structure behind statistical thermodynamics is, in fact, a Lie category.

The theory of Lie groupoids is well studied and have many applications in various area of mathematics like differential geometry, foliation theory, and symplectic geometry. Morita equivalence of Lie groupoids is a flexible and practical concept, providing a convenient framework for developing the foundations of orbifold theory (see [10]). A Morita map (or weak equivalence) between two Lie groupoids $\mathcal{G}(= \mathcal{G}_1 \rightrightarrows \mathcal{G}_0)$ and $\mathcal{H}(= \mathcal{H}_1 \rightrightarrows \mathcal{H}_0)$ consists of a Lie groupoid morphism from \mathcal{G} to \mathcal{H} which is moreover fully faithful and essentially surjective. Furthermore, two Lie groupoids \mathcal{G} and \mathcal{H} are Morita equivalent if and only if there exists a third Lie groupoid \mathcal{K} together with two Morita maps from \mathcal{G} to \mathcal{K} and from \mathcal{H} to \mathcal{K} ([9], [10]). A more explicit description of Morita equivalence \mathcal{G} and \mathcal{H} requires a smooth manifold P and the existence a proper left action of \mathcal{G} on P and a proper right action of \mathcal{H} on P , commuting each other and making P a $\mathcal{G} - \mathcal{H}$ bibundle ([5]).

In this article, we generalize the concept of Morita equivalence from the context of Lie groupoids to Lie categories. We begin by reviewing the basic definitions and examples associated with Lie categories. Then we introduce the concept of functors, equivalence of Lie categories and explore the idea of Morita equivalence of Lie categories.

2 Lie categories

First, we recall the basic definitions and examples of Lie categories needed in this paper, for more details see [2].

Definition 2.1. A *Lie category* is a small category $\mathcal{C} \rightrightarrows \mathcal{X}$, where \mathcal{C} is a smooth manifold with or without boundary, \mathcal{X} is a smooth manifold without boundary, satisfying the following conditions.

- (i) The source and target maps $s, t : \mathcal{C} \rightarrow \mathcal{X}$ are smooth submersions.
- (ii) The unit map $u : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{C}$ and the composition map $m : \mathcal{C}^{(2)} \rightarrow \mathcal{C}$ are smooth, where $\mathcal{C}^{(2)} = \{(g, h) \in \mathcal{C} \times \mathcal{C} : s(g) = t(h)\}$.

(iii) If \mathcal{C} has a boundary, then the restrictions $\partial s, \partial t : \partial\mathcal{C} \rightarrow \mathcal{X}$ of s and t are smooth submersions.

Allowing the space of morphisms in a Lie category to have a boundary is important because this boundary can have a significant impact in both mathematical and physical contexts. This will become clear from the following examples.

Example 2.1. (*Order category*) Consider the category $\mathcal{C} \rightrightarrows \mathbb{R}$, where

$$\mathcal{C} = \{(x, y) \in \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R} : y \leq x\};$$

here the space of morphisms corresponds to the half-plane below the diagonal in \mathbb{R}^2 . Define the source and target maps by the projections to the vertical and horizontal axis respectively, and the composition $m : \mathcal{C}^{(2)} \rightarrow \mathcal{C}$ by

$$m((x, y), (y, z)) = (x, z)$$

Furthermore, the units in \mathcal{C} are exactly the elements on the diagonal, and these are the only invertible elements.

If the object set is singleton, then the Lie category $\mathcal{C} \rightrightarrows \{*\}$ is referred to as a *Lie monoid*. In other words, a Lie monoid is a monoid \mathcal{M} together with a structure of a smooth manifold with or without boundary, such that the multiplication $m : \mathcal{M} \times \mathcal{M} \rightarrow \mathcal{M}$ is smooth. The set $M_n(\mathbb{R})$ of square matrices of order n forms a Lie monoid with matrix multiplication. A *Lie groupoid* is a Lie category in which every morphism is invertible. For example, any smooth manifold M can be viewed as a Lie groupoid, where the objects are the points of M and all morphisms are identity morphisms. Furthermore, every Lie group can be regarded as a Lie groupoid with a single object.

Example 2.2. (*Endomorphism category*) Let (E, p, X) be a vector bundle over a smooth manifold X without boundary. The endomorphism category of (E, p, X) is the Lie category $End(E) \rightrightarrows X$, where the set of morphisms $End(E)$ is defined as

$$End(E) = \{\phi : E_x \rightarrow E_y \mid \phi \text{ is linear and } x, y \in X\}$$

consisting of linear maps between the fibres of (E, p, X) . Here the source and target maps are defined by $s(\phi : E_x \rightarrow E_y) = x$ and $t(\phi : E_x \rightarrow E_y) = y$. The composition of two morphisms $\phi : E_x \rightarrow E_y$ and $\psi : E_y \rightarrow E_z$ is given by $\psi \circ \phi : E_x \rightarrow E_z$.

2.1 Functors and natural transformations

Here, we will introduce functors between Lie categories and natural transformation between them along with some examples.

Definition 2.2. Let $\mathcal{C} \rightrightarrows \mathcal{X}$ and $\mathcal{D} \rightrightarrows \mathcal{Y}$ be two Lie categories. A functor from $\mathcal{C} \rightrightarrows \mathcal{X}$ and $\mathcal{D} \rightrightarrows \mathcal{Y}$ is a functor $F = (F_1, F_0) : (\mathcal{C} \rightrightarrows \mathcal{X}) \rightarrow (\mathcal{D} \rightrightarrows \mathcal{Y})$ of the underlying categories with the property that $F_1 : \mathcal{C} \rightarrow \mathcal{D}$ and $F_0 : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{Y}$ are smooth maps.

Consider two functors $F = (F_1, F_0)$ and $G = (G_1, G_0)$ from $\mathcal{C} \rightrightarrows \mathcal{X}$ to $\mathcal{D} \rightrightarrows \mathcal{Y}$. A smooth map $\tau : F \rightarrow G$ assigns to each object x in \mathcal{X} a morphism $\tau_x : F_0(x) \rightarrow G_0(x)$ in \mathcal{D} , such that for every morphism $f : x \rightarrow y$ in \mathcal{C} , the following diagram commutes:

$$\begin{array}{ccc} F_0(x) & \xrightarrow{\tau_x} & G_0(x) \\ F_1(f) \downarrow & & \downarrow G_1(f) \\ F_0(y) & \xrightarrow{\tau_y} & G_0(y) \end{array}$$

is called a *natural transformation* τ from F to G . A natural transformation τ with every component τ_x is invertible in \mathcal{D} is called a *natural isomorphism*.

For two Lie categories $\mathcal{C} \rightrightarrows \mathcal{X}$ and $\mathcal{D} \rightrightarrows \mathcal{Y}$, all the smooth functors from $\mathcal{C} \rightrightarrows \mathcal{X}$ to $\mathcal{D} \rightrightarrows \mathcal{Y}$ with the smooth natural transformations between them constitute a category called the *functor category* from $\mathcal{C} \rightrightarrows \mathcal{X}$ to $\mathcal{D} \rightrightarrows \mathcal{Y}$ and is denoted by $[\mathcal{C}, \mathcal{D}]$.

Example 2.3. Consider the order category $\mathcal{C} = \{(x, y) \in \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R} : y \leq x\} \rightrightarrows \mathbb{R}$ and its dual $\mathcal{D} = \{(x, y) \in \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R} : x \leq y\} \rightrightarrows \mathbb{R}$. Define $F : (\mathcal{C} \rightrightarrows \mathbb{R}) \rightarrow (\mathcal{D} \rightrightarrows \mathbb{R})$ as follows. Define the object map by $F_0(x) = x$ and morphism map by $F_1(x, y) = (y, x)$. Then $F = (F_1, F_0)$ is a functor of Lie categories.

Example 2.4. Consider the Lie category $\mathcal{C} \rightrightarrows [0, 2\pi)$ where \mathcal{C} is the set of all arcs in S^1 and a morphism from $x \in [0, 2\pi)$ to $y \in [0, 2\pi)$ is an arc from e^{ix} to e^{iy} in S^1 , and is denoted by $\text{arc}(e^{ix}, e^{iy})$, and the source and target maps are given by $s(\text{arc}(e^{ix}, e^{iy})) = x$ and $t(\text{arc}(e^{ix}, e^{iy})) = y$ respectively. The composition is defined by the concatenation of arcs, i.e, $\text{arc}(e^{ix}, e^{iy}) \circ \text{arc}(e^{iy}, e^{iz}) = \text{arc}(e^{ix}, e^{iz})$. Define $G : (\mathcal{C} \rightrightarrows [0, 2\pi)) \rightarrow (\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2 \rightrightarrows \mathbb{R}^2)$ as follows. Define the object map by $G_0(x) = (\cos x, \sin x)$ and the morphism map by $G_1(\text{arc}(e^{ix}, e^{iy})) = ((\cos y, \sin y), (\cos x, \sin x))$. Then $G = (G_1, G_0)$ is a functor.

Define $H : (\mathcal{C} \rightrightarrows [0, 2\pi)) \rightarrow (\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2 \rightrightarrows \mathbb{R}^2)$ as follows. The object map $H_0 : [0, 2\pi) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$ is defined by $H_0(x) = (\cos x, 0)$ and the morphism map by $H_1(\text{arc}(e^{ix}, e^{iy})) = ((\cos y, 0), (\cos x, 0))$. Then $H = (H_1, H_0)$ is a functor.

For the functors $G, H : (\mathcal{C} \rightrightarrows [0, 2\pi]) \rightarrow (\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2 \rightrightarrows \mathbb{R}^2)$, define a function $\alpha : G \rightarrow H$ as follows. For each $x \in [0, 2\pi)$, $\alpha(x) : G(x) \rightarrow H(x)$ is the arrow $((\cos x, \sin x), (\cos x, 0))$ in $\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2$. For any arrow $\text{arc}(e^{ix}, e^{iy})$ in \mathcal{C} , the diagram

$$\begin{array}{ccc} G_0(x) & \xrightarrow{\alpha_x} & H_0(x) \\ G_1(\text{arc}(e^{ix}, e^{iy})) \downarrow & & \downarrow H_1(\text{arc}(e^{ix}, e^{iy})) \\ G_0(y) & \xrightarrow{\alpha_y} & H_0(y) \end{array}$$

is commutative and hence α is a natural transformation from G to H .

2.2 Morita equivalence of Lie categories

In this section, we first discuss the equivalence of Lie categories and then introduce the concept of Morita equivalence.

Definition 2.3. Two Lie categories $\mathcal{C} \rightrightarrows \mathcal{X}$ and $\mathcal{D} \rightrightarrows \mathcal{Y}$ are equivalent if there exists pair of smooth functors $F : (\mathcal{C} \rightrightarrows \mathcal{X}) \rightarrow (\mathcal{D} \rightrightarrows \mathcal{Y})$ and $G : (\mathcal{D} \rightrightarrows \mathcal{Y}) \rightarrow (\mathcal{C} \rightrightarrows \mathcal{X})$ together with natural isomorphisms $I_{\mathcal{C} \rightrightarrows \mathcal{X}} \cong G \circ F$ and $I_{\mathcal{D} \rightrightarrows \mathcal{Y}} \cong F \circ G$.

Example 2.5. Consider the order category $\mathcal{C} = \{(x, y) \in \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R} : y \leq x\} \rightrightarrows \mathbb{R}$ and the endomorphism category $\text{End}(\mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}) \rightrightarrows \mathbb{R}$ of the vector bundle $(\mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}, p, \mathbb{R})$. Define $F : (\mathcal{C} \rightrightarrows \mathbb{R}) \rightarrow (\text{End}(\mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}) \rightrightarrows \mathbb{R})$ as follows. The object map is defined by $F_0(x) = x$ and the morphism map by $F_1(x, y) = \phi_{x,y}$ where $\phi_{x,y} : \{x\} \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \{y\} \times \mathbb{R}$ is given by $\phi_{x,y}(x, r) = (y, r)$. Define $G : (\text{End}(\mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}) \rightrightarrows \mathbb{R}) \rightarrow (\mathcal{C} \rightrightarrows \mathbb{R})$ as follows. Define the object map by $G_0(x) = x$ and the morphism map by $G(\phi_{x,y}) = (x, y)$ if $y \leq x$ and $(0, 0)$ otherwise. Then $G \circ F$ and $F \circ G$ are naturally isomorphic to the identity functors $I_{\mathcal{C} \rightrightarrows \mathbb{R}}$ and $I_{\text{End}(\mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}) \rightrightarrows \mathbb{R}}$ respectively. Hence $\mathcal{C} \rightrightarrows \mathbb{R}$ and $\text{End}(\mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}) \rightrightarrows \mathbb{R}$ are equivalent.

Recall the category **Diff** of smooth manifolds and smooth maps (see [11]). For any Lie category $\mathcal{C} \rightrightarrows \mathcal{X}$ (hereafter, we denote it as \mathcal{C}) there are functors $P^i : \mathcal{C}^{op} \rightarrow \mathbf{Diff}$ given by for each object x and morphism $f : x \rightarrow x'$ in \mathcal{C} , $P_0^i(x) = s^{-1}(x)$ and $P_1^i(f^{op}) : s^{-1}(x') \rightarrow s^{-1}(x)$ by $P_1^i(f^{op})(g') = g' \circ f$, and $P^j : \mathcal{C}^{op} \rightarrow \mathbf{Diff}$ given by for each object x and morphism $f : x \rightarrow x'$ in \mathcal{C} , $P_0^j(x) = t^{-1}(x)$ and $P_1^j(f^{op}) : t^{-1}(x') \rightarrow t^{-1}(x)$ by $f^{op} \circ g$. So, for any Lie category \mathcal{C} , we have the functor category $\mathcal{C}^* = [\mathcal{C}^{op}, \mathbf{Diff}]$.

Now we define Morita equivalence of Lie categories as follows.

Definition 2.4. Two Lie categories \mathcal{C} and \mathcal{D} are Morita equivalent if the functor categories \mathcal{C}^* and \mathcal{D}^* are categorically equivalent.

Example 2.6. Consider the Lie category $\mathbb{R} \rightrightarrows \{*\}$, where the object set is singleton, the morphisms are the real numbers, and the composition is given by the multiplication of the real numbers. Also consider $\mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R} \rightrightarrows \{*\}$, where the object set is singleton, the morphisms are the ordered pairs (r, s) for $r, s \in \mathbb{R}$ and the composition is given by

$$(r, s) \circ (r', s') = (rr', ss')$$

for $(r, s), (r', s') \in \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}$. Then $\mathbb{R}^{op} = \mathbb{R}$ and $(\mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R})^{op} = \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}$. Define

$$F : [\mathbb{R}, \mathbf{Diff}] \rightarrow [\mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}, \mathbf{Diff}]$$

as follows. For an object H in $[\mathbb{R}, \mathbf{Diff}]$, the object map is defined by $F_0(H) : \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbf{Diff}$, where

$$\begin{aligned} F_0(H)(*) &= H_0(*) \times H_0(*) \\ F_0(H)(r, s)(m_1, m_2) &= (H_1(r)(m_1), H_1(s)(m_2)) \end{aligned}$$

Then, for two composable morphisms (r, s) and (r', s') in $\mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}$,

$$\begin{aligned} (F_0(H)(r, s) \circ F_0(H)(r', s'))(m_1, m_2) &= F_0(H)(r, s)((H_1(r')(m_1), H_1(s')(m_2))) \\ &= ((H_1(r)(H_1(r')(m_1)), H_1(s)(H_1(s')(m_2)))) \\ &= (H_1(rr')(m_1), H_1(ss')(m_2)) \\ &= F_0(H)(rr', ss')(m_1, m_2) \\ &= F_0(H)((r, s) \circ (r', s'))(m_1, m_2) \end{aligned}$$

for all $(m_1, m_2) \in H_0(*) \times H_0(*)$, and for the identity morphism $1_* = (1, 1)$ in $\mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}$,

$$\begin{aligned} F_0(H)(1_*)(m_1, m_2) &= F_0(H)(1, 1)(m_1, m_2) \\ &= (H_1(1)(m_1), H_1(1)(m_2)) \\ &= (m_1, m_2) \\ &= 1_{F_0(H)}(m_1, m_2) \end{aligned}$$

$(m_1, m_2) \in H_0(*) \times H_0(*)$. Thus, $F_0(H) : \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbf{Diff}$ is a functor.

To define the morphism map, consider two functors $H, H' : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbf{Diff}$, and a natural transformation $\eta : H \rightarrow H'$ from H to H' . Then $F_1(\eta) : F_0(H) \rightarrow F_0(H')$ is defined in the following way. For the object $*$, $F_1(\eta)(*) : F_0(H)(*) \rightarrow F_0(H')(*)$ is defined by

$$F_1(\eta)(*)(m_1, m_2) = (\eta(*) (m_1), \eta(*) (m_2))$$

for $(m_1, m_2) \in F_0(H)$. Since $\eta(*)$ is smooth, $F_1(\eta)(*)$ is also smooth. For an arrow $(r, s) \in \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}$, the following diagram commutes.

$$\begin{array}{ccc} F_0(H)(*) & \xrightarrow{F_1(\eta)(*)} & F_0(H')(*) \\ F_0(H)(r,s) \downarrow & & \downarrow F_0(H')(r,s) \\ F_0(H)(*) & \xrightarrow{F_1(\eta)(*)} & F_0(H')(*) \end{array}$$

Thus $F_1(\eta)$ is a natural transformation, and hence $F = (F_1, F_0)$ is a functor.

Define $G : [\mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}, \mathbf{Diff}] \rightarrow [\mathbb{R}, \mathbf{Diff}]$ as follows. For each functor $J : \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbf{Diff}$, $G_0(J) : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbf{Diff}$ is defined by,

$$\begin{aligned} G_0(J)(*) &= J_0(*) \\ G_0(J)(r)(n) &= J_1(r, r)(n) \end{aligned}$$

Then, for two composable arrows $r, s \in \mathbb{R}$,

$$\begin{aligned} (G_0(J)(r) \circ G_0(J)(s))(n) &= G_0(J)(r)(J_1(s, s)(n)) \\ &= J_1(r, r)(J_1(s, s)(n)) \\ &= J_1(rs, rs)(n) \\ &= G_0(J)(rs)(n) \end{aligned}$$

for all $n \in J_0(*)$, and for the identity morphism $1_* = 1 \in \mathbb{R}$,

$$G_0(J)(1_*)(n) = G_0(J)(1)(n) = J_1(1, 1)(n) = n = 1_{G_0(J)(*)}(n)$$

for all $n \in J_0(*)$. Then $G_0(J)$ is a functor, and thus the object map is defined.

To define the morphism map, consider two functors $J, J' : \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbf{Diff}$ and the natural transformation $\mu : J \rightarrow J'$ from J to J' . Then, $G_1(\mu) : G_0(J) \rightarrow G_0(J')$ is defined in the following way. For the object $*$, $G_1(\mu)(*) : G_0(J)(*) \rightarrow G_0(J')(*)$ is defined by

$$G_1(\mu)(*)(n) = \mu(n)$$

Since $\mu(*)$ is smooth, $G_1(\mu)(*)$ is also smooth. For each arrow $r : * \rightarrow *$, the following diagram commutes.

$$\begin{array}{ccc} G_0(J)(*) & \xrightarrow{G_1(\mu)(*)} & G_0(J')(*) \\ G_0(J)(r) \downarrow & & \downarrow G_0(J')(r) \\ G_0(J)(*) & \xrightarrow{G_1(\mu)(*)} & G_0(J')(*) \end{array}$$

Thus, $G_1(\mu)$ is a natural transformation, and hence $G = (G_1, G_0)$ is a functor.

We want to show that $G \circ F$ is naturally isomorphic to the identity functor $I_{[\mathbb{R}, \mathbf{Diff}]}$. For a functor $H : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbf{Diff}$, $\alpha(H) : H \rightarrow (G \circ F)(H)$ is defined as follows. For the object $*$, $\alpha(H)(*) : H_0(*) \rightarrow ((G \circ F)_0(H))_0(*)$ is defined by

$$\alpha(H)(*)(m) = (m, m)$$

for $m \in H_0(*)$. For each arrow $r : * \rightarrow *$ in \mathbb{R} , the following diagram commutes.

$$\begin{array}{ccc} H_0(*) & \xrightarrow{\alpha(H)(*)} & ((G \circ F)_0(H))_0(*) \\ H_1(r) \downarrow & & \downarrow ((G \circ F)_0(H))_1(r) \\ H_0(*) & \xrightarrow{\alpha(H)(*)} & ((G \circ F)_0(H))_0(*) \end{array}$$

Thus $\alpha(H)$ is a natural transformation, and $\alpha(H)(*)$ is invertible. So $\alpha : I_{[\mathbb{R}, \mathbf{Diff}]} \rightarrow G \circ F$ is a natural isomorphism.

To show that $F \circ G$ is naturally isomorphic to the identity functor $I_{[\mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}, \mathbf{Diff}]}$, for each functor $J : \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbf{Diff}$, define $\beta(J) : J \rightarrow (F \circ G)(J)$ as follows. For the object $*$, $\beta(J)(*) : J_0(*) \rightarrow ((F \circ G)_0(J))_0(*)$ is defined by

$$\beta(J)(*)(n) = (n, n).$$

for $n \in J_0(*)$. Then, for each arrow (r, s) in $\mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}$, the following diagram commutes.

$$\begin{array}{ccc} J_0(*) & \xrightarrow{\beta(J)(*)} & ((F \circ G)_0(J))_0(*) \\ J_1(r, s) \downarrow & & \downarrow ((F \circ G)_0(J))_1(r, s) \\ J_0(*) & \xrightarrow{\beta(J)(*)} & ((F \circ G)_0(J))_0(*) \end{array}$$

Thus, $\beta(J)$ is a natural transformation, and $\beta(J)(*)$ is invertible. So, $\beta : I_{[\mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}, \mathbf{Diff}]} \rightarrow F \circ G$ is a natural isomorphism. Thus the functor categories $[\mathbb{R}, \mathbf{Diff}]$ and $[\mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}, \mathbf{Diff}]$ are equivalent and hence $\mathbb{R} \rightrightarrows \{*\}$ and $\mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R} \rightrightarrows \{*\}$ are Morita equivalent.

In order to verify that the notion of Morita equivalence for Lie categories coincides with the classical one for Lie groupoids, we briefly recall the Morita theory for Lie groupoids (see [3, 5, 10, 12]).

Definition 2.5 (cf. [5]). A *right action* of a Lie groupoid $\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{G}_1 \rightrightarrows \mathcal{G}_0)$ on a manifold M consists a pair of smooth maps $(a_{\mathcal{G}M}, \mu_{\mathcal{G}M})$, where $a_{\mathcal{G}M} : M \rightarrow \mathcal{G}_0$ (called anchor map) and $\mu_{\mathcal{G}M} : M \times_{a_{\mathcal{G}M}, \mathcal{G}_0, t} \mathcal{G}_1 \rightarrow M$ (where $M \times_{a_{\mathcal{G}M}, \mathcal{G}_0, t} \mathcal{G}_1 = \{(m, g) \in M \times \mathcal{G}_1 : a_{\mathcal{G}M}(m) = t(g)\}$), satisfying

- (1) $\mu_{\mathcal{G}M}(m, 1_{a_{\mathcal{G}M}(m)}) = m$ for all $m \in M$,

(2) $a_{\mathcal{G}M}(\mu_{\mathcal{G}M}(m, g)) = s(g)$ for all $(m, g) \in M \times_{a_{\mathcal{G}M}, \mathcal{G}_0, t} \mathcal{G}_1$, and

(3) $\mu_{\mathcal{G}M}(\mu_{\mathcal{G}M}(m, g), g') = \mu_{\mathcal{G}M}(m, g \circ g')$ for all $(m, g, g') \in M \times_{a_{\mathcal{G}M}, \mathcal{G}_0, t} \mathcal{G}_1 \times_{s, \mathcal{G}_0, t} \mathcal{G}_1$.

A manifold M with the right action of the Lie groupoid \mathcal{G} is called a right \mathcal{G} -manifold. Analogously, one can define the notion of a left \mathcal{G} -manifold.

Example 2.7. For any Lie groupoid \mathcal{G} , the morphism set \mathcal{G}_1 is a right \mathcal{G} -manifold. For, consider the pair $(a_{\mathcal{G}\mathcal{G}_1}, \mu_{\mathcal{G}\mathcal{G}_1})$ where $a_{\mathcal{G}\mathcal{G}_1} : \mathcal{G}_1 \rightarrow \mathcal{G}$ is given by the source map and $\mu_{\mathcal{G}\mathcal{G}_1} : \mathcal{G}_1 \times_{a_{\mathcal{G}\mathcal{G}_1}, \mathcal{G}_0, t} \mathcal{G}_1 \rightarrow \mathcal{G}_1$ is the composition map, gives a right action of \mathcal{G} on \mathcal{G}_1 . Similarly, \mathcal{G}_1 is a left \mathcal{G} -manifold, where the anchor map is given by the target map and action is given by the composition.

Example 2.8. For $g \in \mathcal{G}_1$, the set $M_g = \{g' \in \mathcal{G}_1 : s(g) = t(g')\} = t^{-1}(s(g))$ is a right \mathcal{G} -manifold as follows. Since the target map is a submersion, by submersion level set theorem (Corollary 5.13, [4]), every fibre $t^{-1}(x)$ for $x \in \mathcal{G}_0$ is an embedded submanifold of \mathcal{G}_1 . Therefore, M_g is a submanifold of \mathcal{G}_1 . In particular, M_g is a right \mathcal{G} -manifold with anchor map $a_{\mathcal{G}M_g} : M_g \rightarrow \mathcal{G}_0$ is given by $a_{\mathcal{G}M_g}(g') = s(g')$ and $\mu_{\mathcal{G}M_g} : M_g \times_{a_{\mathcal{G}M_g}, \mathcal{G}_0, t} \mathcal{G}_1 \rightarrow M_g$ is given by $\mu_{\mathcal{G}M_g}(g', g'') = g' \circ g''$.

Let \mathcal{G} be a Lie groupoid, M and N be two right \mathcal{G} -manifolds with actions $(a_{\mathcal{G}M}, \mu_{\mathcal{G}M})$ and $(a_{\mathcal{G}N}, \mu_{\mathcal{G}N})$, respectively. A *right \mathcal{G} -manifold morphism* is a smooth map $f : M \rightarrow N$ satisfying:

(1) $a_{\mathcal{G}N} \circ f = a_{\mathcal{G}M}$.

(2) $f(\mu_{\mathcal{G}M}(m, g)) = \mu_{\mathcal{G}N}(f(m), g)$, for all $(m, g) \in M \times_{a_{\mathcal{G}M}, \mathcal{G}_0, s} \mathcal{G}_1$.

Example 2.9. For $g \in \mathcal{G}_1$, define $f_g : M_g \rightarrow \mathcal{G}_1$ by $f_g(g') = g \circ g'$. Then f_g is a right \mathcal{G} -manifold morphism.

For a manifold M with a right action of a Lie groupoid \mathcal{G} , we denote the action maps by $(a_{\mathcal{G}M}, \mu_{\mathcal{G}M})$. From now on, whenever there is no ambiguity about the manifold M , we write the action maps as $(a_{\mathcal{G}}, \mu_{\mathcal{G}})$. If there is no ambiguity about the Lie groupoid, we use (a_M, μ_M) for the action maps; otherwise, the notation will be specified explicitly.

Definition 2.6 ([5]). Let \mathcal{G} and \mathcal{H} be two Lie groupoids. A *bibundle* from \mathcal{G} to \mathcal{H} is a manifold M together with a left action ν of \mathcal{G} on M , with anchor map $a_{\mathcal{G}} : M \rightarrow \mathcal{G}_0$ and a right action μ of \mathcal{H} on M , with anchor map $a_{\mathcal{H}} : M \rightarrow \mathcal{H}_0$ such that

(1) The map $a_{\mathcal{H}} : M \rightarrow \mathcal{H}_0$ is \mathcal{G} -invariant. i.e, $a_{\mathcal{H}}(\nu(g, m)) = a_{\mathcal{H}}(m)$ for all $m \in M, g \in \mathcal{G}_1$ with $s(g) = a_{\mathcal{G}}(m)$.

- (2) The actions of \mathcal{G} and \mathcal{H} commute. i.e, $\mu(\nu(g, m), h) = \nu(g, \mu(m, h))$ for all $g \in \mathcal{G}_1, m \in M, h \in \mathcal{H}_1$ with $s(g) = a_{\mathcal{G}}(m)$ and $t(h) = a_{\mathcal{H}}(m)$.
- (3) The map $a_{\mathcal{G}} : M \rightarrow \mathcal{G}_0$ is a principal \mathcal{H} - bundle. i.e, the map $a_{\mathcal{G}}$ together with the right action μ of \mathcal{H} on M satisfies the following conditions.
- (a) the map $a_{\mathcal{G}} : M \rightarrow \mathcal{G}_0$ is such that $a_{\mathcal{G}}(\mu(m, h)) = a_{\mathcal{G}}(m)$ for all $(m, h) \in M \times_{a_{\mathcal{H}}, \mathcal{H}_0, t} \mathcal{G}_1$, and
- (b) the map $\phi : M \times_{a_{\mathcal{H}}, \mathcal{H}_0, t} \mathcal{H}_1 \rightarrow M \times_{\mathcal{G}_0} M$ given by $(m, h) \mapsto (h, \mu(m, h))$ is a diffeomorphism.

We denote a \mathcal{G} - \mathcal{H} bibundle M from a Lie groupoid \mathcal{G} to \mathcal{H} by ${}_{\mathcal{G}}M_{\mathcal{H}}$. For any Lie groupoid \mathcal{G} , \mathcal{G}_1 is a $\mathcal{G} - \mathcal{G}$ bibundle.

Definition 2.7 ([5]). Two Lie groupoids \mathcal{G} and \mathcal{H} are Morita equivalent if there is a bibundle ${}_{\mathcal{G}}M_{\mathcal{H}}$ with the action of \mathcal{G} being principal.

Remark 2.1 (Remark 3.33, [5]). For two Lie groupoids \mathcal{G} and \mathcal{H} , if M is a $\mathcal{G} - \mathcal{H}$ bibundle with the action of \mathcal{G} is principal, then there exists a $\mathcal{H} - \mathcal{G}$ bibundle N , where the left action of \mathcal{H} on N is given by the right \mathcal{H} action of M and right action of \mathcal{G} on N is given by the left \mathcal{G} action of M . Indeed, the manifold M remains the same, but the actions switch.

Analogous to the category \mathcal{C}^* of manifold valued presheaves of the Lie category, we consider the category \mathcal{G}^* of manifold valued presheaves of the Lie groupoid \mathcal{G} , where the objects are the smooth functors from \mathcal{G}^{op} to the category of smooth manifolds **Diff** and morphisms are the smooth natural transformations. Further, consider the set of smooth manifolds M where \mathcal{G} can act (from the right), and the smooth maps between the manifolds where the action of \mathcal{G} is preserved. Then this collection forms a category whose objects are right \mathcal{G} -manifolds and morphisms are right \mathcal{G} -manifold morphisms. We denote this category by $Man_{\mathcal{G}}$.

The following lemma shows that for any Lie groupoid \mathcal{G} , the functor category \mathcal{G}^* is equivalent to the category $Man_{\mathcal{G}}$.

Lemma 2.1. *Let \mathcal{G} be a Lie groupoid. The functor category \mathcal{G}^* is categorically equivalent to the category $Man_{\mathcal{G}}$ of the right \mathcal{G} -manifolds.*

Proof. For a Lie groupoid \mathcal{G} , consider the functor category \mathcal{G}^* whose objects are the set $\{P^i : \mathcal{G}^{op} \rightarrow \mathbf{Diff}\}$ of all functors from \mathcal{G}^{op} to **Diff** and morphisms are the set $\{\nu^{ij} : P^i \rightarrow P^j\}$ of natural transformations. Consider the map $F : \mathcal{G}^* \rightarrow Man_{\mathcal{G}}$ given as follows. For an object $P : \mathcal{G}^{op} \rightarrow \mathbf{Diff}$ in \mathcal{G}^* , the object map F_0 is

$$F_0(P) = \bigsqcup_{x \in \mathcal{G}_0} P_0(x),$$

the disjoint union of $P_0(x)$. Then $F_0(P)$ is a smooth manifold as it is the total space of the bundle $(\bigsqcup_{x \in \mathcal{G}_0} P_0(x), p, \mathcal{G}_0)$, where p is the projection. To show that $F_0(P)$ is an object in $Man_{\mathcal{G}}$, we need to define action maps of \mathcal{G} on $F_0(P)$. For let $m \in F_0(P)$, then $m \in P_0(x)$ for $x \in \mathcal{G}_0$. Thus, define the anchor map $a_P : F_0(P) \rightarrow \mathcal{G}_0$ by projecting each element in $P_0(x)$ to x and $\mu_P : F_0(P) \times_{a_P, \mathcal{G}_0, t} \mathcal{G}_1 \rightarrow F_0(P)$ by

$$\mu_P(m, g) = P_1(g^{op})(m)$$

respectively. Then $F_0(P)$ is a right \mathcal{G} -manifold.

Now, consider a natural transformation $\nu^{12} : P^1 \rightarrow P^2$ between the functors $P^1, P^2 : \mathcal{G}^{op} \rightarrow \mathbf{Diff}$. Then, for each $x \in \mathcal{G}_0$, $\nu^{12}(x) : P_0^1(x) \rightarrow P_0^2(x)$ is a smooth map, and for each arrow $g : x \rightarrow y$ in \mathcal{G}_1 , the following diagram commutes.

$$\begin{array}{ccc} P_0^1(x) & \xrightarrow{\nu^{12}(x)} & P_0^2(x) \\ P_1^1(g) \downarrow & & \downarrow P_1^2(g) \\ P_0^1(y) & \xrightarrow{\nu^{12}(y)} & P_0^2(y) \end{array}$$

That is, $\nu^{12}(y) \circ P_1^1(g) = P_1^2(g) \circ \nu^{12}(x)$. We want to show that $F_1(\nu^{12})$ is a right \mathcal{G} -manifold morphism. Define $F_1(\nu^{12}) : F_0(P^1) \rightarrow F_0(P^2)$ by

$$F_1(\nu^{12})(m) = \nu^{12}(x)(m)$$

for $m \in F_0(P^1)$. Since $m \in F_0(P^1)$, $m \in P_0^1(x)$ for some $x \in \mathcal{G}_0$. Then $\nu^{12}(x) : P_0^1(x) \rightarrow P_0^2(x)$ maps each element in $P_0^1(x)$ to an element in $P_0^2(x)$. Thus, $\nu^{12}(x)(m) \in P_0^2(x) \subset F_0(P^2)$. Therefore, $F_1(\nu^{12})$ is defined.

Since $F_0(P^1)$ and $F_0(P^2)$ are right \mathcal{G} -manifolds with action (a_{P^1}, μ_{P^1}) and (a_{P^2}, ν_{P^2}) , for $m \in P_0^1(x) \subset F_0(P^1)$,

$$(1) \quad a_{P^2}(F_1(\nu^{12})(m)) = a_{P^2}(\nu^{12}(x)(m)) = x = a_{P^1}(m).$$

(2) Let $m \in F_0(P^1)$ and $g : x \rightarrow y$ with $a_{P^1}(m) = t(g)$. Then $m \in P_0^1(y)$ and

$$\begin{aligned} F_1(\nu^{12})(\mu_{P^1}(m, g)) &= F_1(\nu^{12})(P^1(g^{op})(m)) \\ &= \nu^{12}(x)(P^1(g^{op})(m)) \\ &= P^2(g^{op})(\nu^{12}(y)(m)) \\ &= P^2(g^{op})(F_1(\nu^{12})(m)) \\ &= \mu_{P^2}(F_1(\nu^{12})(m), g) \end{aligned}$$

(using the fact that ν^{12} is a natural transformation).

Thus $F_1(\nu^{12})$ is a right \mathcal{G} -manifold morphism. Moreover, for two composable morphisms $\nu^{12} : P^1 \rightarrow P^2$ and $\nu^{23} : P_2 \rightarrow P_3$ in \mathcal{G}^* ,

$$F_1(\nu^{12} \circ \nu^{23}) = F_1(\nu^{12}) \circ F_1(\nu^{23})$$

and for each object P in \mathcal{G}^* , $F_1(1_P) = 1_{F_0(P)}$. Hence $F = (F_1, F_0)$ is a functor.

Consider the map $G : \text{Man}_{\mathcal{G}} \rightarrow \mathcal{G}^*$ given as follows. Let M be a right \mathcal{G} -manifold with action (a_M, μ_M) . Then, $G_0(M) : \mathcal{G}^{op} \rightarrow \mathbf{Diff}$ is defined by

$$G_0(M)(x) = a_M^{-1}(x)$$

and for $g : x \rightarrow y$, $G_0(M)(g^{op}) : G_0(M)(y) \rightarrow G_0(M)(x)$ by

$$G_0(M)(g^{op})(m) = \mu_M(m, g),$$

where $m \in G_0(M)(y)$. Then $G_0(M)$ is a functor, and thus object map is defined. Let M and M' be two right \mathcal{G} -manifolds with actions (a_M, μ_M) and $(a_{M'}, \mu_{M'})$, respectively, and $f : M \rightarrow M'$ be a right \mathcal{G} -manifold morphism. To show that $G_1(f) : G_0(M) \rightarrow G_0(M')$ is a natural transformation; for each object $x \in \mathcal{G}_0$, define $G_1(f)(x) : G_0(M)(x) \rightarrow G_0(M')(x)$ by

$$G_1(f)(x)(p) = f(p)$$

for $p \in G_0(M)(x)$. Since f is smooth, $G_1(f)(x)$ is also smooth. Consider an arrow $g : x \rightarrow y$ in \mathcal{G}_1 and the following diagram.

$$\begin{array}{ccc} G_0(M)(y) & \xrightarrow{G_1(f)(y)} & G_0(M')(y) \\ G_0(M)(g^{op}) \downarrow & & \downarrow G_0(M')(g^{op}) \\ G_0(M)(x) & \xrightarrow{G_1(f)(x)} & G_0(M')(x) \end{array}$$

Then for $m \in G_0(M)(y) = a_M^{-1}(y)$,

$$\begin{aligned} (G_1(f)(x) \circ G_0(M)(g^{op}))(m) &= G_1(f)(x)(\mu_M(m, g)) \\ &= f(\mu_M(m, g)) \\ &= \mu_{M'}(f(m), g) \\ &= G_0(M')(g^{op})(f(m)) \\ &= (G_0(M')(g^{op}) \circ G_1(f)(y))(m) \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

Thus $G_1(f)$ is a natural transformation, and for two composable morphisms $f : M \rightarrow M'$ and $f' : M' \rightarrow M''$,

$$G_1(f \circ f') = G_1(f) \circ G_1(f').$$

Also, for each object M in $Man_{\mathcal{G}}$, $G_1(1_M) = 1_{G_0(M)}$. Hence $G = (G_1, G_0)$ is a functor.

For any functor $P : \mathcal{G}^{op} \rightarrow \mathbf{Diff}$, $(G \circ F)(P) = P$ and thus $G \circ F$ is naturally isomorphic to the identity functor $I_{\mathcal{G}^*}$ on \mathcal{G}^* . Moreover, for any right \mathcal{G} -manifold M , $(F \circ G)(M) \cong M$ and thus $F \circ G$ is naturally isomorphic to the identity functor $I_{Man_{\mathcal{G}}}$ on $Man_{\mathcal{G}}$. Hence \mathcal{G}^* and $Man_{\mathcal{G}}$ are equivalent. \square

The following is an illustration of the above lemma.

Consider the unit circle S^1 . Then $S^1 \rightrightarrows S^1$ is a Lie groupoid with objects are the points on the circle S^1 , and the morphisms are only the identity morphisms. Consider the functor P from $(S^1)^{op}$ to \mathbf{Diff} , which maps each point x on the circle to the tangent space $T_x S^1$ of S^1 at x , and each identity morphism maps to the identity maps on the tangent spaces. Then the right S^1 -manifold corresponding to the functor P is the tangent bundle TS^1 .

Conversely, consider a manifold $S^1 \times \mathbb{R}$, the cylinder. Then, $S^1 \times \mathbb{R}$ is a right S^1 -manifold with anchor map $a_{S^1} : S^1 \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow S^1$ is given by the projection to the first component, and the action map $\mu_{S^1} : (S^1 \times \mathbb{R}) \times_{a_{S^1}, S^1, t} S^1 \rightarrow S^1 \times \mathbb{R}$ is given by $\mu((x, r), y) = (x, r)$. Then, the functor P corresponds to $S^1 \times \mathbb{R}$ is given as follows. The object map P_0 is given by

$$P_0(x) = a_{S^1}^{-1}(x) = \{x\} \times \mathbb{R}$$

and the morphism map P_1 is given by

$$P_1(1_x^{op})(x', r) = \mu_{S^1}((x', r), x).$$

Finally, we show that the Morita equivalence of Lie categories holds for Lie groupoids as well.

Theorem 2.1. *Let \mathcal{G} and \mathcal{H} be two Lie groupoids, and \mathcal{G}^* and \mathcal{H}^* be their category of presheaves. Then \mathcal{G} and \mathcal{H} are Morita equivalent as Lie groupoids if and only if the categories \mathcal{G}^* and \mathcal{H}^* are equivalent.*

Proof. Consider two Lie groupoids \mathcal{G} and \mathcal{H} , which are Morita equivalent, then there exists a $\mathcal{G} - \mathcal{H}$ bibundle M such that the action of \mathcal{G} being principal. That is, M is a smooth manifold together with a left action $\nu_{\mathcal{G}M}$ of \mathcal{G} on M , with anchor map $a_{\mathcal{G}M} : M \rightarrow \mathcal{G}_0$ and a right action $\mu_{\mathcal{H}M}$ of \mathcal{H} on M , with anchor map $a_{\mathcal{H}M} : M \rightarrow \mathcal{H}_0$ satisfying the conditions in Definition 2.6. Define $F : Man_{\mathcal{G}} \rightarrow Man_{\mathcal{H}}$ as follows. For a right \mathcal{G} -manifold P with action maps (a_P, μ_P) ,

$$F_0(P) = (P \times_{a_P, \mathcal{G}_0, a_{\mathcal{G}M}} M) / \mathcal{G}$$

where $P \times_{a_P, \mathcal{G}_0, a_{\mathcal{G}M}} M = \{(p, m) \in P \times M : a_P(p) = a_{\mathcal{G}M}(m)\}$. Then $F_0(P)$ is a smooth manifold (see [5]). We denote an element $(p, m)_{\mathcal{G}}$ in the quotient $(P \times_{a_P, \mathcal{G}_0, a_{\mathcal{G}M}} M)/_{\mathcal{G}}$ by $[(p, m)]_{\mathcal{G}}$. To show that $F_0(P)$ is a right \mathcal{H} -manifold, define $a_{F_0(P)} : F_0(P) \rightarrow \mathcal{H}_0$ by

$$a_{F_0(P)}([(p, m)]_{\mathcal{G}}) = a_{\mathcal{H}M}(m)$$

and $\mu_{F_0(P)} : F_0(P) \times_{a_{F_0(P)}, \mathcal{H}_0, t} \mathcal{H}_1 \rightarrow F_0(P)$ by

$$\mu_{F_0(P)}([(p, m)]_{\mathcal{G}}, h) = [p, \mu_{\mathcal{H}M}(m, h)]_{\mathcal{G}}$$

Since $(a_{\mathcal{H}M}, \mu_{\mathcal{H}M})$ is a right action of \mathcal{H} on M , $F_0(P)$ is a right \mathcal{H} -manifold with actions $(a_{F_0(P)}, \mu_{F_0(P)})$. To define the morphism map, consider two right \mathcal{G} -manifolds \mathcal{P} and \mathcal{P}' with actions (a_P, μ_P) and $(a_{P'}, \mu_{P'})$, respectively, and a right \mathcal{G} -manifold morphism $f : P \rightarrow P'$. Define $F_1(f) : F_0(P) \rightarrow F_0(P')$ by

$$F_1(f)([(p, m)]_{\mathcal{G}}) = [(f(p), m)]_{\mathcal{G}}$$

Since $[(p, m)]_{\mathcal{G}} \in F_0(P)$, $a_P(p) = a_{\mathcal{G}M}(m)$. Also, since f is a right \mathcal{G} -manifold morphism, $a_{P'}(f(p)) = a_P(p)$. Thus, $a_{P'}(f(p)) = a_{\mathcal{G}M}(m)$. Therefore, $[(f(p), m)]_{\mathcal{G}} \in F_0(P')$ and thus $F_1(f)$ is defined. Then,

(1) for $[(p, m)]_{\mathcal{G}} \in F_0(P)$,

$$\begin{aligned} a_{F_0(P')}(F_1(f)([(p, m)]_{\mathcal{G}})) &= a_{F_0(P')}([(f(p), m)]_{\mathcal{G}}) \\ &= a_{\mathcal{H}}(m) \\ &= a_{F_0(P)}([(p, m)]_{\mathcal{G}}) \end{aligned}$$

(2) for $([(p, m)]_{\mathcal{G}}, h) \in F_0(P) \times_{a_{F_0(P)}, \mathcal{H}_0, t} \mathcal{H}_1$,

$$\begin{aligned} F_1(f)(\mu_{F_0(P)}([(p, m)]_{\mathcal{G}}, h)) &= F_1(f)([p, \mu_{\mathcal{H}M}(m, h)]_{\mathcal{G}}) \\ &= [f(p), \mu_{\mathcal{H}M}(m, h)]_{\mathcal{G}} \\ &= \mu_{F_0(P')}([(f(p), m)]_{\mathcal{G}}, h) \\ &= \mu_{F_0(P)}(F_1(f)([(p, m)]_{\mathcal{G}}), h). \end{aligned}$$

Thus, $F_1(f)$ is a right \mathcal{H} -manifold morphism. For two composable morphisms $f : P \rightarrow P'$ and $f' : P' \rightarrow P''$ in $Man_{\mathcal{G}}$,

$$F_1(f' \circ f)([(p, m)]_{\mathcal{G}}) = [((f' \circ f)(p), m)]_{\mathcal{G}}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
(F_1(f') \circ F_1(f))([(p, m)]_{\mathcal{G}}) &= F_1(f')([(f(p), m)]_{\mathcal{G}}) \\
&= [(f'(f(p)), m)]_{\mathcal{G}} \\
&= [((f' \circ f)(p), m)]_{\mathcal{G}}
\end{aligned}$$

together imply that $F_1(f' \circ f) = F_1(f') \circ F_1(f)$. Also, for each object P in $Man_{\mathcal{G}}$,

$$F_1(1_P)([(p, m)]_{\mathcal{G}}) = [(1_P(p), m)]_{\mathcal{G}} = [(p, m)]_{\mathcal{G}} = 1_{F_0(P)}([(p, m)]_{\mathcal{G}}).$$

Therefore, $F = (F_1, F_0)$ is a functor.

Since M is a $\mathcal{G} - \mathcal{H}$ bibundle with the action \mathcal{G} is principal, then by Remark 2.1, there exists a $\mathcal{H} - \mathcal{G}$ bibundle N with left \mathcal{H} action $(a_{\mathcal{H}N}, \nu_{\mathcal{H}N})$ and right \mathcal{G} action $(a_{\mathcal{G}N}, \mu_{\mathcal{G}N})$. Now, define $G : Man_{\mathcal{H}} \rightarrow Man_{\mathcal{G}}$ as follows. For a right \mathcal{H} -manifold Q with action maps (a_Q, μ_Q) , define

$$G_0(Q) = (Q \times_{a_Q, \mathcal{H}_0, a_{\mathcal{H}N}} N) / \mathcal{H}.$$

Then, $G_0(Q)$ is a right \mathcal{G} -manifold with right actions $(a_{G_0(Q)}, \mu_{G_0(Q)})$, where $a_{G_0(Q)} : G_0(Q) \rightarrow \mathcal{G}_0$ is given by

$$a_{G_0(Q)}([(q, n)]_{\mathcal{H}}) = a_{\mathcal{G}N}(n)$$

and $\mu_{G_0(Q)} : G_0(Q) \times_{a_{G_0(Q)}, \mathcal{G}_0, t} \mathcal{H}_1 \rightarrow G_0(Q)$ is given by

$$\mu_{G_0(Q)}([(q, n)]_{\mathcal{H}}, g) = [(q, \mu_{\mathcal{G}N}(n, g))]_{\mathcal{H}}$$

For two right \mathcal{H} -manifold Q and Q' with actions (a_Q, μ_Q) and $(a_{Q'}, \mu_{Q'})$, respectively, and a right \mathcal{H} -manifold morphism $j : Q \rightarrow Q'$, $G_1(j) : G_0(Q) \rightarrow G_0(Q')$ is defined by

$$G_1(j)([(q, n)]_{\mathcal{H}}) = [(j(q), n)]_{\mathcal{H}}.$$

Then $G_1(j)$ is a right \mathcal{G} -manifold morphism and thus a morphism in $Man_{\mathcal{G}}$. Also, for two composable morphisms $j : Q \rightarrow Q'$ and $j' : Q' \rightarrow Q''$,

$$G_1(j' \circ j) = G_1(j') \circ G_1(j)$$

and $G_1(1_Q) = 1_{G_0(Q)}$ for each object Q in $Man_{\mathcal{H}}$. Therefore, $G = (G_1, G_0)$ is a functor.

Consider the functor $G \circ F : Man_{\mathcal{G}} \rightarrow Man_{\mathcal{G}}$, which maps each right \mathcal{G} -manifold P to $(G \circ F)_0(P) = (((P \times_{\mu_P, \mathcal{G}_0, a_{\mathcal{G}M}} M) / \mathcal{G}) \times_{\mu_{F_0(P)}, \mathcal{H}_0, a_{\mathcal{H}N}} N) / \mathcal{H}$ and each morphism $f : P \rightarrow P'$ to $(G \circ F)_1(f) : (G \circ F)_0(P) \rightarrow (G \circ F)_0(P')$, and is given by

$$(G \circ F)_1(f)([[[(p, m)]_{\mathcal{G}}, n]]_{\mathcal{H}}) = [[[(f(p), m)]_{\mathcal{G}}, n]]_{\mathcal{H}},$$

and the identity functor $I_{Man_{\mathcal{G}}} : Man_{\mathcal{G}} \rightarrow Man_{\mathcal{G}}$. Define $\tau : G \circ F \rightarrow I_{Man_{\mathcal{G}}}$ as follows. For each object P in $Man_{\mathcal{G}}$, the map $\tau_P : (G \circ F)_0(P) \rightarrow P$ is defined in the following way.

Let $[[(p, m)]_{\mathcal{G}}, n]_{\mathcal{H}} \in (G \circ F)_0(P)$, then $a_{F_0(P)}([[(p, m)]_{\mathcal{G}}]) = a_{\mathcal{H}N}(n)$ and it imply that $a_{\mathcal{H}N}(n) = a_{\mathcal{H}M}(m)$. Thus $(n, m) \in N \times_{\mathcal{H}_0} M$. Since N is a $\mathcal{H} - \mathcal{G}$ bibundle, the map $a_{\mathcal{H}N} : N \rightarrow \mathcal{H}_0$ is a principal \mathcal{H} -bundle. Then there exists a unique $g \in \mathcal{G}_1$ such that $\mu_{\mathcal{G}N}(n, g) = m$ (we use the fact that $M = N$, see Remark 2.1). Now define

$$\tau_P([[(p, m)]_{\mathcal{G}}, n]_{\mathcal{H}}) = \mu_P(p, g).$$

Since $a_P(p) = a_{\mathcal{G}M}(m) = a_{\mathcal{G}M}(\mu_{\mathcal{G}N}(n, g)) = t(g)$, $\mu_P(p, g)$ is defined (we use the fact that the left \mathcal{G} action on M and right \mathcal{G} action on N are same). Then τ_P is a right \mathcal{G} -manifold morphism. For a right \mathcal{G} -manifold morphism $f : P \rightarrow P'$, consider the following diagram.

$$\begin{array}{ccc} (G \circ F)_0(P) & \xrightarrow{\tau_P} & P \\ (G \circ F)_1(f) \downarrow & & \downarrow f \\ (G \circ F)_0(P') & \xrightarrow{\tau_{P'}} & P' \end{array}$$

Then,

$$\begin{aligned} (\tau_{P'} \circ (G \circ F)_1(f))([[(p, m)]_{\mathcal{G}}, n]_{\mathcal{H}}) &= \tau_{P'}([[(f(p), m)]_{\mathcal{G}}, n]_{\mathcal{H}}) \\ &= \mu_{P'}(f(p), g) \\ &= f(\mu_P(p, g)) \\ &= f(\tau_P([[(p, m)]_{\mathcal{G}}, n]_{\mathcal{H}})) \\ &= (f \circ \tau_P)([[(p, m)]_{\mathcal{G}}, n]_{\mathcal{H}}) \end{aligned}$$

Thus, τ is a natural transformation. Since τ_P is invertible for each object P in $Man_{\mathcal{G}}$, and therefore, τ is a natural isomorphism.

Similarly, $F \circ G : Man_{\mathcal{H}} \rightarrow Man_{\mathcal{H}}$ is naturally isomorphic to the identity $I_{Man_{\mathcal{H}}}$, where the natural isomorphism $\delta : F \circ G \rightarrow I_{Man_{\mathcal{H}}}$ is given as follows. For each object Q in $Man_{\mathcal{H}}$, $(F \circ G)_0(Q) = (((Q \times_{\mu_Q, \mathcal{H}_0, a_{\mathcal{H}N}} N)/\mathcal{H}) \times_{\mu_{G_0(Q), \mathcal{G}_0, a_{\mathcal{G}M}} M})/\mathcal{G}$, and for each morphism $j : Q \rightarrow Q'$, $(F \circ G)_1(j) : (F \circ G)_0(Q) \rightarrow (F \circ G)_0(Q')$ is given by

$$(F \circ G)_1(j)([[(q, n)]_{\mathcal{H}}, m]_{\mathcal{G}}) = [[(j(q), n)]_{\mathcal{H}}, m]_{\mathcal{G}}.$$

Then for each object Q in $Man_{\mathcal{H}}$, the map $\delta_Q : (F \circ G)_0(Q) \rightarrow Q$ is given by

$$\delta_Q([[(q, n)]_{\mathcal{H}}, m]_{\mathcal{G}}) = \mu_Q(q, h),$$

where $h \in \mathcal{H}_1$ such that $\mu_{\mathcal{H}M}(m, h) = n$. Therefore, $Man_{\mathcal{G}}$ and $Man_{\mathcal{H}}$ are equivalent. Hence by Lemma 2.1, the functor categories \mathcal{G}^* and \mathcal{H}^* are equivalent.

Conversely, suppose the functor categories \mathcal{G}^* and \mathcal{H}^* are equivalent. By Lemma 2.1, \mathcal{G}^* and $Man_{\mathcal{G}}$ are equivalent and so the categories $Man_{\mathcal{G}}$ and $Man_{\mathcal{H}}$ are equivalent. Thus there exists a functor $F = (F_1, F_0) : Man_{\mathcal{G}} \rightarrow Man_{\mathcal{H}}$ such that F is full, faithful and essentially surjective (see [8]). Since the morphism set \mathcal{G}_1 of \mathcal{G} is a right \mathcal{G} -manifold (see example 2.7) and F is a functor, $F_0(\mathcal{G}_1)$ is a right \mathcal{H} -manifold with the smooth maps $a_{\mathcal{H}} : F_0(\mathcal{G}_1) \rightarrow \mathcal{H}_0$ and $\mu_{\mathcal{H}} : F_0(\mathcal{G}_1) \times_{a_{\mathcal{H}}, \mathcal{H}_0, t} \mathcal{H}_1 \rightarrow F_0(\mathcal{G}_1)$. Since M_g and \mathcal{G}_1 are right \mathcal{G} -manifolds (see examples 2.7 and 2.8), and F is an equivalence,

$$hom_{Man_{\mathcal{G}}}(M_g, \mathcal{G}_1) \cong hom_{Man_{\mathcal{H}}}(F_0(M_g), F_0(\mathcal{G}_1)) \quad (2)$$

For each $g \in \mathcal{G}_1$, we have the right \mathcal{G} -manifold morphism $f_g : M_g \rightarrow \mathcal{G}_1$, which is defined by $f_g(g') = g \circ g'$, for $g' \in M_g$ (see example 2.9). Then $F_1(f_g)$ is a right \mathcal{H} -manifold morphism from $F_0(M_g)$ to $F_0(\mathcal{G}_1)$ (from (2)), and is given by

$$F_1(f_g)(F_0(g')) = F_0(f_g(g')) = F_0(g \circ g').$$

Now, define $a_{\mathcal{G}} : F_0(\mathcal{G}_1) \rightarrow \mathcal{G}_0$ by

$$a_{\mathcal{G}}(F_0(g)) = t(g)$$

and $\nu_{\mathcal{G}} : \mathcal{G}_1 \times_{s, \mathcal{G}_0, a_{\mathcal{G}}} F_0(\mathcal{G}_1) \rightarrow F_0(\mathcal{G}_1)$ by

$$\nu_{\mathcal{G}}(g, F_0(g')) = F_1(f_g)(F_0(g')) = F_0(g \circ g').$$

Then $F_0(\mathcal{G}_1)$ is a left \mathcal{G} -manifold with actions $(a_{\mathcal{G}}, \nu_{\mathcal{G}})$.

To prove $F_0(\mathcal{G}_1)$ is a $\mathcal{G} - \mathcal{H}$ bibundle, consider $F_0(g) \in F_0(\mathcal{G}_1)$ and $g' \in \mathcal{G}_1$ with $a_{\mathcal{G}}(F_0(g)) = s(g')$, then

$$a_{\mathcal{H}}(\nu_{\mathcal{G}}(g, F_0(g'))) = a_{\mathcal{H}}(F_1(f_g)(F_0(g'))) = a_{\mathcal{H}}(F_0(g')).$$

(since $F_1(f_g)$ is a right \mathcal{H} -manifold morphism). Thus, $a_{\mathcal{H}}$ is \mathcal{G} -invariant. Also,

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_{\mathcal{H}}(\nu_{\mathcal{G}}(g, F_0(g')), h) &= \mu_{\mathcal{H}}(F_1(f_g)(F_0(g')), h) \\ &= F_1(f_g)(\mu_{\mathcal{H}}(F_0(g'), h)) \\ &= \nu_{\mathcal{G}}(g, \mu_{\mathcal{H}}(F_0(g'), h)) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

and thus the actions of \mathcal{G} and \mathcal{H} commute. To prove $a_{\mathcal{G}} : F_0(\mathcal{G}_1) \rightarrow \mathcal{G}_0$ is a principal

\mathcal{H} -bundle, consider $(F_0(g), h) \in F_0(\mathcal{G}_1) \times_{a_{\mathcal{H}, \mathcal{H}_0, t}} \mathcal{H}_1$, then

$$\begin{aligned}
a_{\mathcal{G}}(\mu_{\mathcal{H}}(F_0(g), h)) &= a_{\mathcal{G}}(\mu_{\mathcal{H}}(F_0(1_{t(g)} \circ g), h)) \\
&= a_{\mathcal{G}}(\mu_{\mathcal{H}}(\nu_{\mathcal{G}}(1_{t(g)}, F_0(g)), h)) \\
&= a_{\mathcal{G}}(\nu_{\mathcal{G}}(1_{t(g)}, \mu_{\mathcal{H}}(F_0(g), h))) \\
&= t(1_{t(g)}) \\
&= t(g) \\
&= a_{\mathcal{G}}(F_0(g)).
\end{aligned}$$

Thus, $a_{\mathcal{G}}$ is \mathcal{H} -invariant. Consider the map $\phi : F_0(\mathcal{G}_1) \times_{a_{\mathcal{H}, \mathcal{H}_0, t}} \mathcal{H}_1 \rightarrow F_0(\mathcal{G}_1) \times_{\mathcal{G}_0} F_0(\mathcal{G}_1)$ given by

$$\phi(F_0(g), h) = (F_0(g), \mu_{\mathcal{H}}(F_0(g), h)).$$

For $(F_0(g), h), (F_0(g'), h') \in F_0(\mathcal{G}_1) \times_{a_{\mathcal{H}, \mathcal{H}_0, t}} \mathcal{H}_1$,

$$\begin{aligned}
\phi(F_0(g), h) = \phi(F_0(g'), h') &\Rightarrow (F_0(g), \mu_{\mathcal{H}}(F_0(g), h)) = (F_0(g'), \mu_{\mathcal{H}}(F_0(g'), h')) \\
&\Rightarrow F_0(g) = F_0(g') \text{ and } \mu_{\mathcal{H}}(F_0(g), h) = \mu_{\mathcal{H}}(F_0(g'), h')
\end{aligned}$$

Since $(F_0(g), h), (F_0(g'), h') \in F_0(\mathcal{G}_1) \times_{a_{\mathcal{H}, \mathcal{H}_0, t}} \mathcal{H}_1$,

$$a_{\mathcal{H}}(F_0(g), h) = t(h) \text{ and } a_{\mathcal{H}}(F_0(g'), h') = t(h').$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned}
F_0(g) = F_0(g') &\Rightarrow a_{\mathcal{H}}(F_0(g), h) = a_{\mathcal{H}}(F_0(g'), h') \\
&\Rightarrow t(h) = t(h')
\end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
\mu_{\mathcal{H}}(F_0(g), h) = \mu_{\mathcal{H}}(F_0(g'), h') &\Rightarrow a_{\mathcal{H}}(\mu_{\mathcal{H}}(F_0(g), h)) = a_{\mathcal{H}}(\mu_{\mathcal{H}}(F_0(g'), h')) \\
&\Rightarrow s(h) = s(h')
\end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

Thus, (4) and (5) together imply that $h = h'$. Therefore,

$$\phi(F_0(g), h) = \phi(F_0(g'), h') \Rightarrow (F_0(g), h) = (F_0(g'), h'),$$

and hence ϕ is one-one.

To prove ϕ is onto, let $(F_0(g_1), F_0(g_2)) \in F_0(\mathcal{G}_1) \times_{\mathcal{G}_0} F_0(\mathcal{G}_1)$. We have to find $(F_0(g), h) \in F_0(\mathcal{G}_1) \times_{a_{\mathcal{H}, \mathcal{H}_0, t}} \mathcal{H}_1$ such that $\phi(F_0(g), h) = (F_0(g_1), F_0(g_2))$. That is, $(F_0(g), \mu_{\mathcal{H}}(F_0(g), h)) = (F_0(g_1), F_0(g_2))$. Take $F_0(g) = F_0(g_1)$. It is enough to find an $h \in \mathcal{H}_1$ such that $\mu_{\mathcal{H}}(F_0(g_1), h) = F_0(g_2)$. Suppose this is not the case. That is, there exists no arrow $h \in \mathcal{H}_1$ with $a_{\mathcal{H}}(F_0(g_1), h) = t(h)$ such that $\mu_{\mathcal{H}}(F_0(g_1), h) = F_0(g_2)$.

Then there exists no arrow g in $F^{-1}(\mathcal{H}_1)$ with $a_{\mathcal{G}}(g_1) = t(g)$ such that $\mu_{\mathcal{G}}(g_1, g) = g_2$, which is a contradiction since \mathcal{G}_1 is a $\mathcal{G} - \mathcal{G}$ bibundle. Since $\phi = pr_1 \times \mu$ (where pr_1 is the projection onto the first component) and both pr_1 and μ are smooth, ϕ is smooth. Thus ϕ is a diffeomorphism. Thus $a_{\mathcal{G}} : F_0(\mathcal{G}_1) \rightarrow \mathcal{G}_0$ is a principal \mathcal{H} -bundle.

Further, the action of \mathcal{G} on $F_0(\mathcal{G}_1)$ is principal as follows. Since $a_{\mathcal{H}}$ is \mathcal{G} -invariant, it is enough to show that the map $\psi : \mathcal{G}_1 \times_{s, \mathcal{G}_0, a_{\mathcal{G}}} F_0(\mathcal{G}_1) \rightarrow F_0(\mathcal{G}_1) \times_{\mathcal{H}_0} F_0(\mathcal{G}_1)$ given by

$$\psi(g, F_0(g')) = (\nu_{\mathcal{G}}(g, F_0(g')), F_0(g'))$$

is a diffeomorphism.

$$\text{For } (g_1, F_0(g'_1)), (g_2, F_0(g'_2)) \in \mathcal{G}_1 \times_{s, \mathcal{G}_0, a_{\mathcal{G}}} F_0(\mathcal{G}_1),$$

$$\begin{aligned} \psi((g_1, F_0(g'_1))) = \psi(g_2, F_0(g'_2)) &\Rightarrow (\nu_{\mathcal{G}}(g_1, F_0(g'_1)), F_0(g'_1)) = (\nu_{\mathcal{G}}(g_2, F_0(g'_2)), F_0(g'_2)) \\ &\Rightarrow \nu_{\mathcal{G}}(g_1, F_0(g'_1)) = \nu_{\mathcal{G}}(g_2, F_0(g'_2)) \text{ and } F_0(g'_1) = F_0(g'_2) \end{aligned}$$

Since $(g_1, F_0(g'_1)), (g_2, F_0(g'_2)) \in \mathcal{G}_1 \times_{s, \mathcal{G}_0, a_{\mathcal{G}}} F_0(\mathcal{G}_1)$,

$$a_{\mathcal{G}}(F_0(g'_1)) = s(g_1) \text{ and } a_{\mathcal{G}}(F_0(g'_2)) = s(g_2).$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned} F_0(g'_1) = F_0(g'_2) &\Rightarrow a_{\mathcal{G}}(F_0(g'_1)) = a_{\mathcal{G}}(F_0(g'_2)) \\ &\Rightarrow s(g_1) = s(g_2) \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \nu_{\mathcal{G}}(g_1, F_0(g'_1)) = \nu_{\mathcal{G}}(g_2, F_0(g'_2)) &\Rightarrow a_{\mathcal{G}}(\nu_{\mathcal{G}}(g_1, F_0(g'_1))) = a_{\mathcal{G}}(\nu_{\mathcal{G}}(g_2, F_0(g'_2))) \\ &\Rightarrow t(g_1) = t(g_2). \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

Thus, (6) and (7) imply that $g_1 = g_2$. That is,

$$\psi((g'_1, F_0(g_1))) = \psi(g'_2, F_0(g_2)) \Rightarrow ((g'_1, F_0(g_1))) = (g'_2, F_0(g_2)),$$

which gives ψ is one one. To prove ψ is onto, consider an element $(F_0(g_1), F_0(g_2))$ in $F_0(\mathcal{G}_1) \times_{\mathcal{H}_0} F_0(\mathcal{G}_1)$. We have to find an element $(g, F_0(g'))$ in $\mathcal{G}_1 \times_{s, \mathcal{G}_0, a_{\mathcal{G}}} F_0(\mathcal{G}_1)$ such that $\psi(g, F_0(g)) = (F_0(g_1), F_0(g_2))$. That is, $(\nu_{\mathcal{G}}(g, F_0(g')), F_0(g')) = (F_0(g_1), F_0(g_2))$. Take $F_0(g') = F_0(g_2)$. It is enough to find a $g \in \mathcal{G}$ such that $\nu_{\mathcal{G}}(g, F_0(g_2)) = F_0(g_1)$. i.e, $F_0(g \circ g_2) = F_0(g_1)$. Since \mathcal{G}_1 is a $\mathcal{G} - \mathcal{G}$ bibundle, for any $g_1, g_2 \in \mathcal{G}_1$, there exists $g \in \mathcal{G}_1$ such that $g \circ g_2 = g_1$. Therefore, take $g = g_1 \circ g_2^{-1}$. Then,

$$F_0(g \circ g_2) = F_0((g_1 \circ g_2^{-1}) \circ g_2) = F_0(g_1)$$

Thus, ψ is onto. Since $\psi = \nu \times pr_2$ (where pr_2 is the projection on to the second component) and both ν and pr_2 are smooth, ψ is smooth. Therefore, ψ is a diffeomorphism.

That is, $F_0(\mathcal{G}_1)$ is a $\mathcal{G} - \mathcal{H}$ bibundle with the action of \mathcal{G} is principal and hence \mathcal{G} and \mathcal{H} are Morita equivalent as Lie groupoids.

□

3 Conclusion

We defined the Morita equivalence of Lie categories and provided an example to illustrate it. Additionally, we verified that our definition is valid for Lie groupoids. Lie groupoids are used to represent stacks ([5]), which are generalized spaces that account for symmetry. Morita equivalence helps ensure that different presentations of a stack represent the same underlying object. This is particularly useful in the theory of orbifolds ([5, 10]), which are spaces that locally look like the quotient of a manifold by a group action. Moving forward, we plan to explore the implications of relaxing the invertibility in Lie groupoids.

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Author Contribution declaration

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The authors declare that they have no competing interests

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